

The Naphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium Cation Reactions with Nucleophilic Species

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Manuscript received 10 April 1986, revised 29 January 1987, accepted 10 July 1987

The preparation and some facile reactions of 2-ethylnaphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium cation with nucleophilic species are described. The cation is shown to react rapidly in aqueous solution with a variety of nucleophiles yielding 2-hydroxy-*N*-ethylnaphthimido derivatives. With carboxylate, cyanate or thiocyanate anions, internal rearrangements occur, converting the imido adducts to *O*-substituted products.

2-Ethylnaphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium tetrafluoroborate (1) obtained following the published method^{1,2} is shown to react in aqueous solutions within the pH range 3–7 with a variety of nucleophiles, such as hydrosulphide, cyanide, methoxide and azide ions yielding 2-hydroxy-*N*-ethylnaphthimido derivatives (Scheme 1). The reactions of these nucleophiles with naphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium cation receive ready rationalisation in terms of the initial formation of ketoketenimine³. The great facility of the reaction is illustrated by the rapid combination of the azide ion in aqueous solution to give the precursor the imidoazide (2c) whose subsequent cyclisation to the observed tetrazole (3c) may be regarded as proceeding from an intramolecular 1,3-dipolar addition⁴.

The formation of 2-hydroxy-*N*-ethylthionaphthamide from 2-ethylnaphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium cation and hydrosulphide ion can best be rationalised as proceeding via the naphthoketoketenimine (ii).

The hydrosulphide anion acting as a base in the first instance, abstracts a proton at the 3-position of the naphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium cation to generate an ylide (i). The formation of the ylide is accompanied by rapid ring opening to give the naphthoketoketenimine (ii). Hydrosulphide ion then attacks the naphthoketoketenimine nucleophilically across the reactive cumulative system of the ketoketenimine to form stable thioamide tautomer, namely 2-hydroxy-*N*-ethylthionaphthamide (3a). The structure of 3a gets support from the methylene resonance of *N*-ethylthioamide function which showed octet as a result of interaction of methylene protons with methyl protons and NH proton, implying that the substance exists predominantly as its thioamide tautomer.

Similarly, compound 1 when reacted with methoxide and azide yielded 3b and 3c through the intermediate 2b and 2c. With cyanide ion, the final product was 3d. The structure of the compounds (3a–d) were established by spectral data (see experimental).

Scheme 1

With more complex bifunctional nucleophiles such as the cyanate (2e) and thiocyanate (2f) anions, the initial imido adducts 2e and 2f can undergo internal rearrangements converting the imido adducts into cyclic urethane (3e) and thiourethane (3f).

N-Ethylnaphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium fluoroborate reacts with extraordinary facility with carboxylate ions such as benzoate, acetate, hippurate and methoxyacetate anions in aqueous solutions, giving a white crystalline substance in a few minutes, in almost quantitative yield. On the basis of spectral evidence and elemental analysis, the products of various carboxylate anion reactions were assigned the structure 2-*O*-acyl-*N*-ethylnaphthamide (3g) formed through the intermediary of an iminoanhydride (2g) by means of an acyl shift^{5,6}.

Experimental

2-Hydroxyethylthionaphthamide (3a): A solution of sodium sulphide hydrate (4 g, 1.7×10^{-2} mol) in

water (5 ml) was treated with slightly more than 1 equivalent hydrochloric acid and mixed with a solution of *N*-ethyl-naphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium fluoborate (**1**; 0.5 g, 1.7×10^{-3} mol) in acetonitrile (2 ml). After 10 min, a green yellow suspension was extracted with dichloromethane (4×10 ml). The extracts were pooled and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The green-yellow solution was concentrated to give a yellow crystalline solid (0.35 g, 86%), m.p. $82 - 3^\circ$ (Found: C, 67.47; H, 5.65; N, 5.95. $C_{13}H_{13}NOS$ requires: C, 67.5; H, 5.62; N, 6.06%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (N-H stretch), 1 500 (N-H bend), 1 270 (C-N), 1 220 (C-O) and $1 190 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=S); δ (CDCl₃) ca 1.25 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.8 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.15 (6H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, d, OH). On deuteration of the sample with a few drops of D₂O the δ 8.2 peak due to OH proton disappeared.

Methyl-2-hydroxy-1-naphthoate (3b): A solution of **1** (0.5 g, 1.7×10^{-3} mol) in methanol (12 ml) was stirred vigorously during the addition of a solution of sodium methoxide (prepared by dissolution of 50 mg sodium metal in 3.3 ml absolute methanol). When the addition was completed, the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. $40 - 60^\circ$; 5×10 ml). The residue obtained by evaporating the petroleum ether extracts was crystallised from methanol to give the crystalline product (0.33 g, 94%), m.p. 80° (Found: C, 71.18; H, 4.98. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ requires: C, 71.28; H, 4.95%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 080 (C-H stretch in aromatic), 2 985 (C-H stretch in alkyl group), 1 665 (C=O) and $1 230 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-O); δ (CDCl₃) 4.15 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.5 (6H, m, ArH), and 8.7 (1H, d, OH). On deuteration of the sample with a few drops of D₂O the δ 8.7 peak due to OH proton disappeared.

2-Hydroxy-N-ethyl-naphthimidoazide (2c) and 1-ethyl-2-(2-hydroxynaphthyl)tetrazole (3c): A solution of **1** (0.5 g, 1.7×10^{-3} mol) in acetonitrile (2 ml) was added to a stirred ice-cold solution of sodium azide (1.5 g, 0.023 mol) in water (15 ml). The resulting lemon-yellow suspension was rapidly extracted with cold carbon tetrachloride (2×5 ml). The organic layers were quickly combined and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The infrared spectrum taken on the lemon-yellow solution showed a strong azide absorption at 2 020 and C=N at $1 625 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. On leaving to stand for 20 minutes at room temperature, the yellow colouration disappeared and a white solid separated, which was filtered off and recrystallised from acetonitrile, (3.97 g, 94.5%), m.p. 203° (Found: C, 65.1; H, 4.91; N, 23.32. $C_{13}H_{12}N_4O$ requires: C, 65; H, 5.0; N, 23.33%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 200-3 500 (OH), 1 630 (C=N), 1 340 (C-N) and $1 230 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-O); δ (CDCl₃) 1.3 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.3 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.7 (6H, m, ArH) and 9.5 (1H, s, OH). On deuteration of the sample with few drops of D₂O the δ 9.5 peak due to OH proton disappeared.

2-Hydroxy-N-ethyl-naphthimidonitrile (2d): An overlayer of n-pentane (10 ml) was added to an

aqueous solution (20 ml) of sodium cyanide (2.5 g, 0.05 mol) during vigorous stirring. A solution of **1** (1.2 g, 4.2×10^{-3} mol) in acetonitrile (10 ml) was then added to it. The organic layer was separated while the aqueous layer extracted with n-pentane (2×10 ml). The extracts were pooled, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated, yielding a crystalline solid. Crystallisation from ethanol gave bright orange crystals which were filtered and dried (0.75 g, 75%), m.p. 73° (Found: C, 74.8; H, 5.2; N, 12.3. $C_{14}H_{12}N_2O$ requires: C, 75; H, 5.36; N, 12.5%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 250 (C=N stretch) and $1 630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=N); δ (CCl₄) 1.2 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.3 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.7 (6H, m, ArH) and 8.5 (1H, d, OH). On deuteration of the sample with a few drops of D₂O the δ 8.5 peak due to OH proton disappeared.

1-Ethylimino-1H-naphth[1,2-e][1-3]oxazine-3(2H)-one: A solution of *N*-ethyl-naphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium fluoborate (0.5 g, 1.7×10^{-3} mol) in acetonitrile (2.5 ml) was added to a solution of potassium cyanate (2.5 g, 10^{-2} mol) in water (5 ml). The milky suspension so formed was extracted with dichloromethane (3×5 ml). The extracts were pooled, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was then evaporated. The residue was recrystallised from acetonitrile to give a crystalline solid (0.35 g, 86%), m.p. 190° (Found: C, 69.81; H, 4.96; N, 11.68. $C_{14}H_{12}N_2O_2$ requires: C, 70.00; H, 5.0; N, 11.6%); ν_{max} 3 330 (N-H stretch), 1 715 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N), 1 220 (C-O) and 1 130 (C-N); δ (CDCl₃) ca 1.4 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.8 (2H, q, CH₂) and 7.8 (6H, m, ArH).

1-Ethylimino-1H-naphtho[1,2-e][1,3]oxazine-3-(2H)-thione: A solution of *N*-ethyl-naphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium fluoborate (1 g, 3.52×10^{-3} mol) in acetonitrile (4 ml) was added to aqueous 20% solution of sodium thiocyanate (7 ml). The resulting turbid yellow mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (3×10 ml). The extracts were pooled and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was stripped off and the residue recrystallised from chloroform, (0.85 g, 95%), m.p. 210° (Found: C, 65.45; H, 4.66; N, 10.85; S, 12.45. $C_{14}H_{12}N_2OS$ requires: C, 65.62; H, 4.63; N, 10.93; S, 12.5%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (N-H stretch), 3 080 (C-H stretch in aromatic system), 2 985 (C-H stretch in alkyl), 1 640 (C=N stretch), 1 560 (N-H bending), 1 240 (C-O), 1 130 (C-N), 1 105 and $1 050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=S); δ (CDCl₃) ca 1.4 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.8 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.8 (1H, s, NH) and 7.8 (6H, m, ArH).

2-O-Acetyl-N-ethyl-naphthamide: A solution of sodium acetate (1.6 g) in water (12 ml) was adjusted to pH 5.5 by addition of dilute HCl, and *N*-ethyl-naphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium fluoborate (0.5 g, 1.7×10^{-3} mol) was added to it slowly as fine powder with stirring. The resulting white solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from dichloromethane to give a white crystalline solid (0.42 g, 93.3%), m.p. 195° (Found: C, 69.85; H, 5.84; N, 5.48. $C_{15}H_{15}NO_3$ requires: C, 70.00; H, 5.8; N, 5.4%) ν_{max} (KBr)

3 300 (N-H stretch), 1 766 and 1 650 (C=O), 1 640 (N-H bend), 1 400 (C-N stretch) and 1 200 cm^{-1} (C-O-C stretch); δ (CDCl_3) *ca* 1.3 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.3 (3H, s, COOCH_3), 3.6 (2H, q, CH_2), 6.0 (1H, NH) and 7.6 (6H, m, ArH)

2-O-benzoyl-N-ethyl-naphthamide ($R=Ph$): The substitution of benzoate ion, in the procedure described for the reaction with acetate ion, afforded a white crystalline solid (90%), m.p. 201° (Found: C, 75.1; H, 5.13; N, 4.24. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires: C, 75.23; H, 5.33; N, 4.38%).

2-O-methoxyacetyl-N-ethyl-naphthamide ($R=\text{CH}_3\text{-OCH}_2$): The substitution of methoxyacetate ion, in procedure described for the reaction with acetate ion, afforded a white solid (90%), m.p. 198° (Found: C, 70.91; H, 6.3; N, 5.2. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires: C, 70.85; H, 6.27; N, 5.16%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 780 (ester C=O) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (amide C=O).

2-O-hippuryl-N-ethyl-naphthamide ($R=Ph\text{CONH-CH}_2$): Hippuric acid (7.0 g, 0.039 mol) was dissolved in 1N NaOH (40 ml). The resulting solution was adjusted to pH 5 by the addition of dilute

HCl and stirred rapidly while adding finely powdered *N*-ethyl-naphth[1,2-*d*]isoxazolium fluoborate (7.0 g, 0.028 mol). The resulting suspension was extracted with dichloromethane (3×25 ml), which were then pooled, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated. The resulting solid was recrystallised from dichloromethane, (6.5 g, 62%) m.p. 227° (Found: C, 71.0; H, 5.31; N, 7.31. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 70.2; H, 5.31; N, 7.44%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 770 (ester C=O) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (amide C=O).

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